

COMPOSITES GROWN IN SITU FROM THE SOLID STATE

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Abstract

In-situ composites can be obtained by unidirectional eutectic solidification. Unidirectional decomposition in the solid state is a newer and still less developed technique. Methods of solid-state growth may be classified according to the state of the starting material in

- a. eutectoid decomposition
- b. precipitation from solid solution
- c. growth from the non-crystalline state

The advantages of the new techniques are the many more composite systems thereby made possible, the extension of the suitable composition range and the decrease of the interphase spacing in comparison with eutectic composites. Solid state decomposition makes it also possible to reinforce an object, after it has been shaped by mechanical means. The disadvantages are the difficult practical techniques to be used and suggest that the growth process from the solid state is more promising in the production of composites for non-structural than for structural application.

1. Introduction

The basic principle of preparing aligned in-situ composites is the decomposition of a single phase material. The starting material can be either liquid or solid (figure 1). Where a liquid is concerned the composite material is grown by unidirectional solidification of a eutectic melt. This is the oldest and still most extensively used technique. The limitations of this method are the limited range of compositions for which regular composites are obtained and the rather large distances between lamellae or rods of one phase.

In 1970 the unidirectional decomposition of crystalline solids was introduced and this has extended the number of systems and decreased the interphase distance (1). The experimental technique of unidirectional decomposition of eutectoids and of supersaturated solid solutions is essentially the same as that of unidirectional solidification. Recently another technique for preparing in-situ composites from the solid state was developed involving unidirectional growth from the vitreous and amorphous states (17). In this technique quenched-in liquids of salts and oxides or vapor-quenched metals are heated until decomposition into two crystalline phases occurs.

In this paper the latter techniques are described and the results evaluated. The solid state decomposition processes are classified as follows:

1. eutectoid decomposition (section 2)
 2. precipitation from the solid solution (section 3)
 3. growth from the non-crystalline state (section 4)
- The advantages and disadvantages will be discussed briefly in the last section.

2. Eutectoid decomposition

The eutectoid decomposition of a single solid phase into an aggregate of two crystalline solids is similar to eutectic solidification. The most striking difference is the state of aggregation of the parent phase. Unidirectional eutectic solidification can be compared with single-phase crystal growth from the melt in a sense that an isothermal front of the crystalline product phase(s) moves parallel to the direction of heat flow. Depending on the characteristics and the volume ratio of the product phases aligned structures

are obtained with lamellae or fibres parallel to the growth direction, i.e. parallel to the temperature gradient.

With essentially the same technique aligned lamellar composites can be produced by unidirectional decomposition of eutectoids (1,2). When the crystalline eutectoid parent phase is decomposed in a temperature gradient the product phases grow parallel to the gradient into the parent phase (figure 2). This means that the growth direction is determined in the first place by the temperature gradient and not by a possible orientation relationship between the crystal structures of parent and product phases.

2.1 Experimental procedure

The generation of composites by eutectoid decomposition consists of two steps:

- I the preparation of the parent eutectoid phase;
- II the decomposition of the parent eutectoid phase.

I. Because grain boundaries influence the resulting microstructures (see below), it is clear that the best lamellar structures are obtained by starting from a single-crystal eutectoid parent material. When the high temperature alloy freezes congruently from the melt, single-crystal starting material for eutectoid decomposition can easily be obtained by unidirectional solidification. In this way the starting materials for decomposition of the Cu-Al (2,3) and Ni-In (5,6) eutectoids have been produced. The directional solidification technique may also be used in systems where the eutectoid parent phase melts peritectically like the Co-Si (1,5,7), Cu-In (1) and Fe-Al (7) eutectoids, but restrictions have to be put on the ratio of temperature gradient over growth rate in order to suppress dendritic growth.

Where it is difficult to get single crystalline starting material, it is usually sufficient to start from a parent phase with a large grain size. Large grain sizes may be obtained by prolonged annealing just below the melting point (1). In many of the more recently reported directional decompositions the starting materials consist of such large grains obtained by annealing, e.g. in case of the Cu-Al (8) and the Cu-In (9) eutectoid.

II. The procedure of directional decomposition of the

eutectoid parent phase is analogous to the directional eutectic solidification: the material is cooled down in a temperature gradient from temperatures above the eutectoid temperature to temperatures well below the decomposition temperature. It is performed by pulling the samples from a heater to a cooler or by passing a hot zone through the solid eutectoid sample. The temperature gradients used are mostly between 50 and 400°C/cm. The velocities of translation through the gradient with which aligned composites can be produced are strongly dependent on the specific eutectoid system (section 2.2). The rates reported in the literature vary from 10^{-2} to 10^2 cm/hr.

The directional eutectoid decomposition is more complex than its eutectic analogue, because of the non-isotropic nature of the parent phase. Although the direction of heat flow is of first importance for the growth direction, certain orientation relationships may exist between parent and product phases. Probably these relationships are responsible for the lamellar morphology which is predominantly found. In the system Cu-Al they cause minor deviations of the lamellar orientations with respect to the pulling direction, resulting in a zigzag structure (3).

When the parent phase consists of grains, the resulting lamellae in one grain are mutually parallel and parallel to the temperature gradient. Perpendicular to the gradient, the lamellae in the different original grains have different orientations (figure 3). When the original parent grains are very small, repeated nucleation ahead of the isothermal front may disturb the lamellar orientation, giving rise to unaligned microstructures. The finer the grain size, the higher the temperature gradient necessary to suppress the random nucleation (3). Insufficiently high temperature gradients were the main reason of failure to align pearlite until 1970, when Bolling and Richman (4) succeeded in partly aligning the Fe-C eutectoid decomposition by using a gradient of 3000°C/cm. Large gradients together with large differences between high and low temperatures not only impede nucleation ahead of the growth front, but they may also prevent rapid coarsening behind the transformation front (9).

2.2 Limits of eutectoid growth

Compared with the technique to obtain composites by

directional eutectic solidification the process of eutectoid decomposition has the following characteristics:

1. Fewer eutectoids have been aligned so far. The reason is trivial: fewer eutectoids are known than eutectics and furthermore the effort put into eutectics to date is much higher.
2. The eutectoid morphology obtained is predominantly lamellar (section 2.1).
3. The interlamellar spacing under the same growth conditions in eutectoid structures is smaller by a factor of 10 to 100.
4. The influence of the growth rate on the eutectoid interlamellar spacing is less pronounced than on the eutectic spacing (figure 4).
5. The maximum translation velocity with which aligned structures may be obtained (R_{\max}) by eutectoid decomposition is usually smaller than in the case of eutectic solidification and strongly coupled to the eutectoid temperature (T_E) (Table 1).
6. The smallest period found in aligned eutectoids is of the order of $10^{-1} \mu\text{m}$; this limit is reached in eutectic systems by growing with ultra high rates.
7. The composition range for aligned off-eutectoid decomposition increases more rapidly with increasing growth rate than in the case of off-eutectic solidification.

Table 1

Eutectoid temperature (T_E) and maximum translation velocity (R_{\max}) of the systems investigated.

<u>System</u>	Pb-Sn [*]	Cu-Al	Cu-In	Ni-In	Co-Si
T_E (°K)	421	438	847	1043	1443
R_{\max} (cm/hr)	0.16	0.5	1.9	7.0	>12.0

^{*}The Pb-Sn system concerns a precipitation reaction. In this case T_E means the equilibrium decomposition temperature.

Model

These features of the unidirectional eutectoid decomposition can be explained by considering a kinetic model of the eutectoid reaction (5,10,11,12). Underlying the model are three basic assumptions:

- a. grain boundary diffusion in the growing front

between parent and product phases provides the atomic rearrangement in the transformation process;
 b. the product phases tend to achieve local equilibrium with the parent phase;
 c. the large supercooling of the growing front with respect to the eutectoid temperature is due to the kinetics of the growth process.

According to the model the advancing lamellae propagate into the parent phase with a microscopically flat growth front which is perpendicular to the growth direction (figure 5). Because of the equilibrium condition (b), the maximum difference in concentration in the parent phase just ahead of the front of the alternate lamellae (Δc) can be related to the total supercooling (ΔT) as

$$\Delta c = \frac{2\Delta T}{\tan \varphi} \quad , \quad (1)$$

where $\tan \varphi$ is the mean absolute value of the slopes of the solvi. Having set the boundary conditions one can formulate the fluxes J (figure 5) and find an expression for Δc in terms of interlamellar period (λ) and growth rate (R)

$$\Delta c = k\lambda^2 R \quad , \quad (2)$$

where k is a constant (in a temperature range small compared with T_E). The supercooling in a stepwise growth process is related to the growth rate as

$$R = k'(\Delta T)^2 \quad , \quad (3)$$

where k' is a constant (again in a small temperature range). Combining eqs. (1), (2) and (3) yields:

$$\lambda^4 R = \text{constant} \quad (4)$$

Discussion

Equation (4) indicates a slower decrease in eutectoid spacings with increasing growth rates than in eutectic ones, where almost all experimental data fit

$\lambda^2 R = \text{constant}$. Equation (4) has been verified experimentally for several eutectoid systems, whereas also some deviating experimental data have been reported (figure 4). However, a closer look at many experimental results reveals that the data reported cover

R-ranges with different slopes of the λ -R curves (11,13). The theoretical relationship (eq. 4) will not be confirmed when the translation velocity of the samples through the temperature gradient differs from the actual velocity of the growth front. It can be shown by calculation that the experimental data should fit the curve of figure 6.

Some experimental data reported indicate that a different mechanism may play a role. For example, in the Cu-In system (9) the experimental data tend to fit $\lambda^2 R = \text{constant}$ at very small growth rates. This may indicate that the process is volume diffusion controlled at small growth rates, that is at small supercoolings.

The critical value in the λ -R curve (figure 6) is around $R=R_{\text{max}}$. This maximum possible translation velocity is equal to the maximum possible growth rate of the lamellae in the parent phase. The growth rate shows a maximum at a certain supercooling where the increasing driving force on increasing supercooling matches the decreasing diffusivity on decreasing temperatures. We have calculated this dependence and shown that R_{max} is a rather strong function of the eutectoid temperature, which accounts for the data of table 1.

The minimum spacing which can be obtained in aligned eutectoid composites will be at the maximum translation velocity. Substitution of reasonable values in the constant of equation 4 yields

$$\lambda_{\text{min}} \approx 0.1 \text{ } \mu\text{m} \quad (10)$$

which is in agreement with the experimental data.

The kinetics of the eutectoid process requires a much larger supercooling than in eutectic solidification. This has been verified experimentally by relating the data of isothermal to isovelocity experiments (e.g. 4,8,13). In agreement with the theories of coupled growth, this causes a much more rapid increase of the composition range for aligned off-eutectoid composite growth than for off-eutectic growth (14).

Conclusion

Unidirectional eutectoid decomposition should be seen as an additional technique to produce aligned in-situ composites. An advantage of this technique over that

of eutectic solidification is that under the same growth conditions the interlamellar periods are smaller. They are also less dependent on the growth rate. The composition range of aligned eutectoids and off-eutectoids, especially at higher velocities, is usually larger than of eutectics and off-eutectics. Another property of eutectoid decomposition which may be a disadvantage is the dependence of the resulting structure on the crystallographic orientation of the parent phase. Furthermore the coupling of the maximum growth rate to the eutectoid temperature is a disadvantage, because one needs fairly high eutectoid temperatures to produce composites with a reasonable rate.

3. Precipitation from supersaturated solid solutions

When a solid solution is cooled down below the solubility curve precipitation will occur (figure 1). Precipitation reactions can be divided into continuous and discontinuous reactions. In the first process, the growing precipitates change the composition of the parent phase continuously towards the equilibrium concentration. In discontinuous precipitation reactions, the two product phases with equilibrium concentrations grow together with a single growth front into the parent phase. The phase separation occurs in or just ahead of the advancing front and the matrix does not change in composition.

3.1 Continuous precipitation

Continuous precipitation can be subdivided according to the nucleation processes:

- a. spinodal decomposition (no nucleation)
- b. homogeneous nucleation
- c. heterogeneous nucleation

Often the experimental results after precipitation do not allow a clear distinction between (a) and (b), but in most cases (c) can be clearly recognized.

a. Spinodal decomposition. In spinodal processes there exists a strong orientation relation between the resulting microstructure and the orientation of the parent phase. Especially when the parent phase is isotropic external influence on the structure is expected to be possible. In a way analogous to the aligned eutectoid decomposition (section 2) we have tried to align spinodal decomposition in the Au-Ni

system (50 at % Ni) by means of a temperature gradient (15). The gradient was between 1000 and 2000°C/cm, the translation velocity was varied from 10^{-1} to 1 cm/hr. The results (figure 7) showed coarse precipitates on the grain boundaries of the parent phase and fine precipitates in the grains. The coarse precipitation was continuous with a heterogeneous nucleation, the fine one was interpreted as spinodal decomposition. Neither in the coarse, nor in the fine precipitation there was any alignment with respect to the gradient. The coarse precipitation could be prevented by quenching the solid solution to a temperature of about 300°C below the solubility curve (the spinodal is suppressed by coherency stress). But still no alignment of the spinodal precipitation by the temperature gradient was found.

Spinodal decomposition may be aligned by other driving forces than temperature gradients. For example, alnico alloys are aligned by a magnetic field. Also the later stages of spinodal precipitation can be influenced by applied mechanical stresses (16). These techniques will not be discussed here.

b. Homogeneous nucleation. In the case of homogeneous nucleation the precipitates are nucleated throughout the material. External fields may influence the growth of the precipitates as expected and mentioned above for the spinodal decomposition. We have applied high thermal gradients (between 1000 and 2000°C/cm) on the precipitation of Co out of the solid solution in CoAl (15). The results indicated that some alignment occurred (figure 8) which was absent without the gradient but the alignment obtained was not uniform throughout the samples, which was probably due to deviations of the direction of the thermal gradient on microscale.

c. Heterogeneous nucleation. When heterogeneous nucleation is restricted to grain boundaries, it is possible to nucleate preferentially on specific boundaries by using a thermal gradient or a mechanical stress. Preferential nucleation may induce an oriented precipitation. This technique will not be discussed.

3.2 Discontinuous precipitation

The process of discontinuous precipitation is very similar to that of eutectoid decomposition. The

lamellae of both the precipitating and the equilibrium matrix phase grow contiguously into the parent solid solution. The lamellae can be aligned in the same way as in the eutectoid decomposition.

We have aligned the Sn and Pb lamellae precipitating with a flat isothermal transformation front from a supersaturated Sn solution in Pb (1) (figure 9). Because of the low volume fraction of the Sn phase the lamellae are broken into platelets. As in eutectoid decomposition there exists a maximum translation velocity in the Pb-Sn system above which no alignment occurs. Table 1 shows that this maximum velocity is very low. Presumably this is related to the equilibrium decomposition temperature in the same way as in the eutectoid case.

Other aligned discontinuous precipitations are not yet known. The precipitation of Zn from a supersaturated Fe solution could not be aligned in a normal experimental set-up (temperature gradient below 200°C/cm), probably because of the small grain size of the parent phase (15). Because of the similarity to eutectoid decomposition, the restrictions in both processes are supposed to be the same.

4. Growth of composites from the non-crystalline solid state

The newest preparation technique of in-situ composites is the unidirectional decomposition of non-crystalline solids (17). The basic principle of the technique is the strong dependence of atomic mobility on temperature. At low temperatures, where there is no mobility, a non-crystalline phase which is not in thermodynamic equilibrium will neither crystallize nor decompose. Increasing temperature means increasing mobility. At sufficiently high temperature diffusion will start and the phase changes will occur. The result may be a single crystalline phase. But, when a single crystalline phase of the same composition is not thermodynamically stable, the result may consist of two crystalline solids or one crystalline solid in a non-crystalline matrix. It is also possible that first a single phase crystallizes which subsequently decomposes.

We have shown that in a number of systems the two solids crystallize in one process out of the non-crystalline matrix and that the occurring lamellae or

rods can be aligned by a temperature gradient.

4.1 Experimental procedure

The process consists of two major steps

I the preparation and

II the decomposition

of the non-crystalline phase.

I. Non-crystalline solids can be obtained by quenching or splatcooling of liquids, sputtering or vapour quenching, electrolytic deposition, etc. We have used the most simple method of quenching from the melt and the splat cooling. The absence of crystalline phases was checked by X-ray analyses.

II. Heating vitreous or amorphous samples at a temperature where diffusion can take place results in crystallization and/or decomposition with in general a random orientation of the new phases. Orientation of the resulting structures can be obtained by decomposing in a temperature gradient. As in the eutectic and eutectoid growth, the samples can be moved from a region with high temperatures to one of low temperatures (down-gradient or normal gradient method). However, in the process of growth from the metastable non-crystalline phase the dependence of growth rate on temperature is just opposite to its dependence in eutectic and eutectoid processes. Thus the technique of pulling from low to high temperatures (up-gradient method) becomes obvious.

Down-gradient technique (figure 10a). Local heating of the non-crystalline sample provides nuclei of the final phases. Further growth of the nuclei is prevented by quenching. The pre-nucleated lamellae are then allowed to grow out in a temperature gradient at a temperature, where no random nucleation occurs, but where crystal growth takes place. Moving the sample towards the lower temperature region yields lamellar growth towards the high temperature end only. The result is a lamellar structure aligned parallel to the temperature gradient.

A disadvantage of this method is that the front position is unstable. When the translation velocity is lower than the rate, with which the front moves into the parent phase, the front temperature will increase, resulting in an accelerating front rate. The structure will mostly be unoriented. When on the other

hand the translation velocity is too high for the front to follow, the front temperature will decrease, resulting in a growth stop. Thus minor fluctuations of the translation velocity are amplified in the growth rate and structure control in this way is very difficult.

Up-gradient technique (figure 10b). When samples are moved from a region of low temperature to one of high temperature nucleation will take place somewhere in the gradient, where the temperature is sufficiently high for nucleation. The lamellae will grow out towards all directions, but the rate will decrease when the lamellae grow towards the cold side and will be maximum towards the hot side. Moving the sample towards the hot side will enable the lamellae which are growing towards the cold side to keep on growing at a rate equal to the pulling rate provided the pulling rate is not too high. The position of the front is stable: increase of the pulling rate increases the temperature of the front and thus the growth rate. For the same reason a decreasing pulling rate yields a decreasing growth rate at a lower front temperature. As a consequence the up-gradient technique is easy to control.

4.2 Results

Structures are shown in figures 11 and 12. The lamellae or platelets are parallel to the gradient. The systems aligned to date are listed in Table 2.

Table 2

List of composites obtained from the non-crystalline state. All starting materials have been obtained by quenching except Pd-Si, which was splatcooled.

<u>System</u>	<u>Composition (in mole %)</u>
$\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-RbNO}_3$	61.5; 75% $(\text{RbNO}_3)_2$
$\text{ZnCl}_2\text{-KCl}$	40% KCl
$\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3\text{-B}_2\text{O}_3$	50 % B_2O_3
$\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3\text{-GeO}_2$	90% GeO_2
$\text{Li}_2\text{O-B}_2\text{O}_3$	72.6; 75.8; 85.7; 91.2 % B_2O_3
Pd-Si	

The most striking point of the technique of growth from the non-crystalline state is that it enables in-situ composites to be grown far from the eutectic or eutectoid composition and even in systems (or parts of systems) without a eutectic or eutectoid. Vitreous samples in the $\text{Li}_2\text{O}-\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$ system have been decomposed in quite a large range of compositions (figure 13) (18). Because of the large composition range in which regular structures can be obtained it is possible to change the morphology of the same phases when changing the composition range (figure 14). When the surface energy is isotropic, it forces a lamellar structure to break up if the volume fraction of one of the phases is about $1/3$ or less.

4.3 Comparison with unidirectional eutectic solidification

The results are quite similar to the microstructures obtained by directional eutectic solidification. The question arises whether growth from the non-crystalline solid state is not eutectic solidification at large supercooling.

Similarities

1. The growth process of the two crystalline phases from the non-crystalline phase is a one-step process in the systems investigated. There are, however, indications that other systems may first crystallize and later decompose. The second step is then comparable with eutectoid growth.
2. The lamellae grow contiguously with a planar, isothermal front into the parent phase.
3. The interlamellar spacing (λ) decreases when the growth rate (R) increases. Early experiments in the $\text{Li}_2\text{O}-\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$ system point towards a $\lambda^2 R = \text{constant}$ relationship, although the exponent of λ is uncertain. In the eutectic solidification the same relationship holds. There the constant contains the diffusion coefficient. If the constant for the non-crystalline solid case also contains the diffusion coefficient, smaller spacings may be expected compared to solidification under the same conditions. We studied this in the eutectic nitrate system (61.2 mole % $(\text{RbNO}_3)_2$) and found a decrease of an order of magnitude.

Differences

1. In growth from the non-crystalline solid phase the composition range in which aligned composites can be obtained is very much larger than in growth from the melt. This has been shown e.g. in the nitrate system (75 mole % $(\text{RbNO}_3)_2$) where only a dendritic structure could be obtained from the melt while an aligned lamellar structure resulted from the vitreous state.
2. In growth from the melt, the growth rate increases on increasing the supercooling, which means on decreasing the temperature of the front. In growth from the non-crystalline solid state, the growth rate increases on increasing the temperature. We have measured the dependence of growth rate on temperature and found a nearly exponential behaviour (figure 15) which indicates that the diffusivity is growth rate determining.

Conclusion

The similarities of and differences between growth from the melt and growth from the non-crystalline solid state indicate that the processes are related. However, the kinetics and experimental techniques are so far apart that in-situ growth of composites from the non-crystalline solid state may be regarded as a different and new technique.

5. Evaluation of the techniques for growing aligned composites from the solid state

When evaluating the unidirectional decomposition of solids two major features should be mentioned:

1. The techniques provide a number of new systems and compositions to align where unidirectional eutectic solidification fails. The large possible composition range attainable from non-crystalline solids and the possible change of morphology are especially very difficult or impossible to achieve in eutectic solidification.
2. The spacings in composites from the solid state are mostly 10 to 20 times smaller compared with those attainable with eutectic solidification under the same growth conditions. In case of aligned continuous precipitation the interphase spacings even go down to values which cannot be obtained by solidification.

An advantage for structural application is that an

object can be reinforced by decomposition after it has been shaped in its final form, which is very difficult in the eutectic process.

There are, however, also disadvantages. The most important one in the non-crystalline solid decomposition is the process to produce the starting material. In most cases the methods are limited to the production of thin films. Application of these composites for mechanical purposes does not look very promising. In the case of non-structural applications this factor is of less importance. A second general disadvantage of solid state decomposition compared with eutectic solidification may be the slower reactions which cause lower growth rates under the same circumstances.

In conclusion we may say that unidirectional decomposition of solids have opened up a large new range of suitable compositions and systems for the preparation of in-situ composites. Especially in the case of composites for non-structural application the techniques are promising.

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1. Schematic phase diagram with eutectic (x_1, T_1) , eutectoid (x_2, T_2) and precipitation from a super-saturated solid solution (x_3, T_3) .

2. Co-Co₂Si composite obtained by unidirectional eutectoid decomposition; section and lamellae parallel to temperature gradient.

3. Co-Co₂Si composite obtained by unidirectional eutectoid decomposition; section perpendicular to temperature gradient.

4. The dependence of interlamellar period (λ) on growth rate (R) for eutectics and eutectoids.

5. Schematic growth front and diffusion fluxes (J) in the process where the eutectoid phase γ decomposes into $\alpha + \beta$; the coordinate system moves with velocity R in the z -direction.

6. Theoretically expected relationship between period (λ) and translation velocity (R); below R_{\max} the translation velocity and the growth rate are equal.

7. Continuous precipitation in the Au-Ni system (50 wt% Ni). a. decomposed at about 700°C; b. decomposed at about 400°C.

8. Continuous precipitation of Co from supersaturated CoAl (15 wt% Al); replica; direction of temperature gradient unknown.

9. Discontinuous precipitation of Sn-lamellae from a supersaturated solid solution in Pb; section perpendicular to the temperature gradient.

10. Techniques for growth from the non-crystalline solid state; a. down-gradient method; b. up-gradient method.

11. $\text{Li}_2\text{O}-\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$ composite (85.7 mole% B_2O_3) obtained from the non-crystalline solid state; section and lamellae parallel to temperature gradient.

12. $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3\text{-GeO}_2$ composite (90 mole % GeO_2) obtained from the non-crystalline solid state; section and platelets parallel to temperature gradient.

13. Part of the phase diagram of the $\text{Li}_2\text{O-B}_2\text{O}_3$ system; the crosses indicate compositions and decomposition temperatures of samples investigated.

14. $\text{Li}_2\text{O} \cdot 4\text{B}_2\text{O}_3\text{-B}_2\text{O}_3$ composite; section parallel to temperature gradient; a. 96 wt % B_2O_3 ; b. 93.3 wt % B_2O_3 ; (the lamellae of b. have also been identified in perpendicular sections).

15. The growth rate as a function of front temperature in the $\text{Li}_2\text{O-B}_2\text{O}_3$ system with 85.7 mole % B_2O_3 (two different samples).